

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP1 – Moving beyond pregnancy registries to enhance our understanding of disease related pregnancy outcomes, medication use and safety of use during pregnancy

D1.6 Overview of submitted manuscripts/abstracts of all five demonstration projects

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¹ Please choose the appropriate reference and delete the rest:

R = Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER = Software, technical diagram, etc.

² Please choose the appropriate reference and delete the rest:

PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web;

CO = Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement;

CI = Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

Document History

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V1.0	03 Dec 2024	First Draft	Anja Geldhof, Julie Scotto
V2.0	16 Dec 2024	Final Version	Anja Geldhof, Amanda Neville

Abstract

There are five demonstration projects examining medications taken during pregnancy performed in Work Package 1. An overview of the submitted manuscripts/abstracts with the results for each of the 5 demonstration projects is provided. The outcomes of the demonstration projects, including any medication utilisation and/or safety findings are summarized, along a link to the relevant publications.

Methods

The demonstration projects were selected according to the following criteria - high public health importance; addresses known knowledge gaps; sufficient variety (including established vs new medications, chronic vs acute conditions, rare vs common conditions) to create innovative methodological approaches and involve new data sources. Data sources were selected based upon feasibility and data quality. The five demonstration projects each aimed to integrate multiple aspects for each therapeutic area i.e. medication use in pregnancy and in women of childbearing age; the impact of maternal disease on maternal, perinatal and childhood outcomes; and the impact of medications (medication classes) during pregnancy on these outcomes. While one therapeutic area took the lead for one specific methodological innovation, methods and lessons learned were shared between demonstration projects.

The following is an overview of the five demonstration projects as they were implemented within the timelines of the project:

- The aim of the first demonstration project was to account for “disease bias”, with respect to the underlying disease of neuropathic pain (NP). An algorithm to determine indication for treatment considered essential information, such as the drug name and dosage, the prescriber specialty, patient diagnoses and comedications. The algorithm was developed to identify maternal conditions related to gabapentinoid prescriptions. The utilisation of these medications during pregnancy and their safety of use were also explored.
- The second demonstration project aimed to study long-term neurodevelopmental (ND) outcomes between ages 3-16; and the additional problem of confounding by exposure during breastfeeding (a potential mediator for ND). The ND outcomes of interest were attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), autism spectrum disorder (ASD), intellectual disability (ID) and delayed development (DD). Algorithms were also developed to identify maternal depression before, during and after pregnancy.
- The third demonstration project focus was how to address diseases with very low prevalence and exposure, therefore low sample size. Among women of childbearing age, five algorithms were tested to identify Multiple Sclerosis (MS), and three methods were evaluated for calculating MS prevalence. The effect of different lookback periods on prevalence estimates was assessed. Additionally, the use of MS medications during pregnancy and congenital anomalies linked to maternal MS and Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE), along with their associated treatments, were explored.
- The fourth demonstration project aimed to demonstrate solutions for studying intermittent medication exposures in diseases with episodic manifestations during pregnancy, using medications among women with migraine in pregnancy as the applied example. The outcomes included gestational diabetes and preeclampsia.
- The fifth demonstration project studied incidence and survival of breast cancer in pregnancy to provide guidance on how to evaluate safety of medicine used in diseases that require histopathological data for accuracy. The project particularly focused on improving methods

for inclusion of medicines administered at hospitals which are rarely available in European databases. The project used cancer registries as state-of-the-art data sources for identifying incident cancers, and beyond to assess management of disease. A large data set with geographical diversity together with novel approaches such as multiple imputation were applied to improve measurement of medication exposure and to handle missing data in clinical prognostic factors in multinational settings.

Each demonstration project went through the following steps: data characterization, protocol writing, obtaining data access, developing algorithms for exposure/outcomes/confounder data, writing and implementing statistical analyses plans, and presenting results via a final study reports and/or abstracts and/or manuscripts.

Each DP Lead provided a summary of the abstracts and manuscripts completed for their respective demonstration project.

Results

Below is a list of relevant publications from each DP, with a summary of the main results:

DP1: **Methods for controlling by indication for prescriptions: application to medications for neuropathic pain**

Congress Publications	Brief Summary of Findings
Beau AB, Paoletti O, Bénévent J et al, Reason for gabapentinoids prescribing in pregnancy: results from five European countries A contribution from the IMI ConcePTION project. <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.</i> 2024;33 (S2): e5891. https://doi.org/10.1002/pds.5891	Our study provides valuable insights into gabapentinoid use during pregnancy, with anxiety being the most common condition among pregnant women with gabapentinoid prescriptions in Finnish, Italian, Spanish and Wales data, whereas neuropathic pain predominated in French and Norwegian data. Moreover, we found that between 3% and 23% of these pregnancies were associated with substance misuse and abuse, underscoring the need for careful prescribing of commonly abused medicines. The proposed methods for detecting maternal conditions related to prescribing will facilitate accurate assessment of medication use and safety during pregnancy, whilst addressing confounding by indication.
Beau AB, Mo J, Moisset X et al, A systematic review of gabapentinoids use during pregnancy and effects on pregnancy and childhood outcomes: an IMI ConcePTION study <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.</i> 2024;33 (S2): e5891. https://doi.org/10.1002/pds.5891	Our systematic review comprehensively analyses all available data on the use and safety of gabapentinoids during pregnancy, incorporating data from 27 high-quality studies. Prenatal exposure to pregabalin is associated with an increased risk of congenital anomalies and long-term neurodevelopmental outcomes while gabapentin exposure was associated with an increased risk of preeclampsia, preterm birth and small-for-gestational age. Larger studies are needed to confirm these

	<p>data and explore additional outcomes. The combined evidence from this systematic review and animal studies raises concerns about the safety of using gabapentinoids during pregnancy. Careful evaluation of the benefit-risk balance for both mother and fetus/infant is essential when these medications cannot be avoided during pregnancy.</p>
<p>Beau AB, Cifuentes Castro EA, Karki S, Gabapentinoids exposure in early pregnancy and risk of congenital anomalies a ConcePTION European case-malformed control study, <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.</i> 2024;33 (S2): e5891. https://doi.org/10.1002/pds.5891</p>	<p>Using EUROmediCAT data, we conducted a case malformed-control study based on 254,146 registrants with CAs from livebirths, fetal deaths (≥ 20 weeks) and terminations of pregnancy for fetal anomaly in 12 European countries (1995–2020), covering around 13 million births.</p> <p>This large European study found infrequent first-trimester gabapentinoid exposure ($n = 37$), but identified a potential association with ventricular septal defect, a specific type of cardiac anomaly. While our findings align with some previous studies suggesting teratogenic risks associated with gabapentinoids, they also reveal the challenges of studying rare exposures and outcomes.</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Brief Summary of Findings</p>
<p>Beau A-B, Mo J, Moisset X, Bénévent J, Damase-Michel C. Systematic review of gabapentinoid use during pregnancy and its impact on pregnancy and childhood outcomes: a ConcePTION study. <i>Therapies.</i> 2024 Oct 18;S0040-5957(24)00165-3. doi: 10.1016/j.therap.2024.10.049. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 39567326.</p>	<p>Our systematic review comprehensively analyses all available data on the use and safety of gabapentinoids during pregnancy, incorporating data from 27 high-quality studies. Prenatal exposure to pregabalin is associated with an increased risk of congenital anomalies and long-term neurodevelopmental outcomes while gabapentin exposure was associated with an increased risk of preeclampsia, preterm birth and small-for-gestational age. Larger studies are needed to confirm these data and explore additional outcomes. The combined evidence from this systematic review and animal studies raises concerns about the safety of using gabapentinoids during pregnancy. Careful evaluation of the benefit-risk balance for both mother and fetus/infant is essential when these medications cannot be avoided during pregnancy.</p>

<p>Beau A-B, Paoletti O, Benevent J, Beslay M, Moisset X, Ballardini E, Barrachina-Bonet L, Cavero-Carbonell C, Coldea A, García-Villodre L, Geldhof A, Gini R, Gissler M, Jordan S, Leinonen M, Manfrini M, Martikainen V, Mitter V, Morris J, Neville A, Nordeng H, Puccini A, Mo J, Damase-Michel C. Identifying Maternal Conditions Related to Gabapentinoid Prescriptions in Pregnancy Using Electronic Health Records from Six European Countries - A contribution from the IMI ConcePTION project. <i>Submitted to Drug Safety</i></p>	<p>Our study provides valuable insights into gabapentinoid use during pregnancy, with anxiety being the most common condition among pregnant women with gabapentinoid prescriptions in Finnish, Italian, Spanish and Wales data, whereas neuropathic pain predominated in French and Norwegian data. Moreover, we found that between 3% and 23% of these pregnancies were associated with substance misuse and abuse, underscoring the need for careful prescribing of commonly abused medicines. The proposed methods for detecting maternal conditions related to prescribing will facilitate accurate assessment of medication use and safety during pregnancy, whilst addressing confounding by indication.</p>
<p>A-B Beau, E Cifuentes Castro, J Benevent, M Beslay, M-C Addor, J Bergman, C Cavero-Carbonell, H Dolk, E Garne, M Gatt, J Hoareau, E Den Hond, A Latos-Bielenska, N Lelong, M O'Mahony, X Moisset, J Morris, A J Neville, A Pierini, M Loane, C Damase-Michel. Risk of specific congenital anomalies after gabapentin or pregabalin use in first trimester of pregnancy: an IMI ConcePTION European case-malformed control study. <i>In preparation</i></p>	<p>Using EUROmediCAT data, we conducted a case malformed-control study based on 254,146 registrants with CAs from livebirths, fetal deaths (≥ 20 weeks) and terminations of pregnancy for fetal anomaly in 12 European countries (1995–2020), covering around 13 million births. This large European study found infrequent first-trimester gabapentinoid exposure ($n = 37$), but identified a potential association with ventricular septal defect, a specific type of cardiac anomaly. While our findings align with some previous studies suggesting teratogenic risks associated with gabapentinoids, they also reveal the challenges of studying rare exposures and outcomes.</p>

DP2: Exposure to SSRI/SNRI and depression in pregnancy and long-term childhood outcomes: the effect of modifying factors

Publications	Brief Summary of Findings
<p>Given J, Bromley RL, Coste F, Lopez-Leon S, Loane M (2022) An inventory of European data sources to support pharmacoepidemiologic research on neurodevelopmental outcomes in children following medication exposure in pregnancy: A contribution from the ConcePTION project. PLoS ONE 17(10): e0275979. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0275979</p>	<p>We identified 90 data sources across 14 countries, which contained information on five domains of neurodevelopment – infant development, child behaviour, cognitive, education and ND disorders. This inventory is invaluable to future studies planning to investigate the impact of medication exposures during pregnancy on neurodevelopmental outcomes.</p>
<p>Jordan S, Jones E, Komninou S, Loane M, Damase Michel C. [Editorial] Families need</p>	<p>Few medicines are licensed for use during lactation and there may be no reports of safe</p>

<p>support to reduce the risk of adverse drug reactions from breastfeeding, <i>Pharmaceutical Journal</i>, 7 December 2022. https://pharmaceutical-journal.com/article/opinion/families-need-support-to-reduce-the-risk-of-adverse-drug-reactions-from-breastfeeding</p>	<p>administration to neonates. The Cumberlege Report details how case reports of valproate teratogenicity from the 1980s were not actioned for decades. Analyses of large population databases would militate against such oversights, but first, whole-population data on breastfeeding must be collected. Regular medicine-specific monitoring would detect problems early enough to pre-empt serious problems and offer parents reassurance regarding the safety of medicines during breastfeeding.</p>
<p>Jordan S, Bromley R, Damase-Michel C, Given J, Komninou S, Loane M, Marfell N, Dolk H. Breastfeeding, pregnancy, medicines, neurodevelopment, and population databases: the information desert. <i>Int Breastfeed J</i> 17, 55 (2022). https://doi.org/10.1186/s13006-022-00494-5</p>	<p>The scarcity of whole-population data and the complexities of the inter-relationships between breastfeeding, co-exposures and infant outcomes are significant barriers to full characterisation of the benefits and harms of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding. This makes it difficult to answer the questions: ‘is it safe to breastfeed whilst taking this medicine’, and ‘will this medicine interfere with breastfeeding and/ or infants’ development’?</p>
<p>Given J, Paoletti O, Bromley R, Afonso A, Ballardini E, Beau AB, Bartolini C, Caillet A, Coldea A, Damase-Michel C, Evans HT, Grace E, Jordan S, Leinonen MK, Lupattelli A, Manfrini M, Martikainen V, Morris JK, Neville AJ, Nordeng H, Puccini A, Coste F, Loane M Prevalence of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder and Autism Spectrum Disorder in secondary healthcare data in five European countries: A Contribution from the ConcePTION project. <i>In preparation.</i></p>	<p>There was considerable variation in the time periods covered, follow-up available, and the prevalence of ADHD and ASD in administrative data in the five European countries/regions. While specialist diagnoses are key to identifying children with these disorders, primary care diagnoses and prescription data enables researchers to identify more affected children. It would not be recommended to use primary care data alone. The proportion of ADHD diagnoses that would be missed by using only prescription data varies considerably and depends on the prescribing practice within the country.</p>

DP3: Rare diseases and small sample sizes: Application to Multiple Sclerosis (MS) and Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) in pregnancy.

Congress Publications	Brief Summary of Findings
<p>Beslay M, Beau AB, Bénévent J et al, Identifying women of childbearing age with Multiple Sclerosis in six European HealthCare databases A contribution from the IMI-ConcePTION project, <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.</i> 2024;33 (S2): e5891. https://doi.org/10.1002/pds.5891</p>	<p>This study demonstrates how different algorithms can be used to identify multiple sclerosis in women of childbearing age and pregnant women within healthcare data sources. It also provides new prevalence data for MS in European countries with good</p>

	<p>geographic spread. The least restrictive algorithm, requiring at least one diagnosis of MS, or one prescription/dispensing for MS-specific medicine most closely approximated the published MS prevalences in the respective countries. These insights could contribute to further research on MS medication use in women of childbearing age and pregnant women and on the safety of use of MS medication during pregnancy.</p>
<p>Beslay M, Cifuentes Castro EA, Karki S, et al. Specific Congenital Anomalies Associated with Maternal Multiple Sclerosis: A ConcePTION European Case-Malformed Control Study. <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.</i> 2024;33 (S2): e5891. https://doi.org/10.1002/pds.5891</p>	<p>To assess the risk of congenital anomalies (CAs) associated with maternal MS, we performed a case-malformed control study using data from the EUROmediCAT central database including livebirths, fetal deaths from 20 weeks gestational age, and terminations of pregnancy for fetal anomaly. Maternal Multiple Sclerosis was over-represented among the gastroschisis cases (3 cases). However, considering the small number of cases, and as maternal illness is known to be under-recorded in the central database, these findings require further investigation and verification in other independent datasets.</p>
<p>Karki S, Beslay M, Cifuentes-Castro E et al. The occurrence of specific congenital anomalies associated with maternal Systemic Lupus Erythematosus: A ConcePTION Case-malformed control study in EUROmediCAT. <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.</i> 2024;33 (S2): e5891. https://doi.org/10.1002/pds.5891</p>	<p>To assess the risk of Congenital Anomalies (CA) associated with a maternal diagnosis of Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE), we performed a case-malformed control study using data from the EUROmediCAT central database including livebirths, fetal deaths from 20 weeks gestational age, and terminations of pregnancy for fetal anomaly. This study suggests an increased reporting of maternal SLE among the spina bifida and abdominal wall defects CA subgroups. However, the number of cases of specific CA were very few in EUROmediCAT. Considering the small number of exposed cases, results should be interpreted with caution. Further, the findings can serve as a safety signals that need further research to establish a causal relation..</p>

Publications	Brief Summary of Findings
<p>Marie Beslay, Yvonne Geissbühler, Anna-Belle Beau, Davide Messina, Justine Benevent, Elisa Ballardini, Laia Barrachina-Bonet, Clara Caverro-Carbonell, Alex Coldea, Laura García-Villodre, Anja Geldhof, Rosa Gini, Kerstin Hellwig, Sue Jordan, Maarit K Leinonen, Sandra Lopez-Leon, Marco Manfrini, Visa Martikainen, Vera R Mitter, Amanda J Neville, Hedvig Nordeng, Aurora Puccini, Sandra Vukusic, Joan K Morris, Christine Damase-Michel. Methods of estimating Prevalence of Multiple Sclerosis in six European healthcare data sources: A contribution from the ConcePTION project. <i>Submitted to Eur. J Epidemiology</i></p>	<p>This study assessed the impact of the lookback period and calculation method on prevalence of Multiple Sclerosis (MS) in three healthcare data sources including women of childbearing age (from Italy, Norway and Wales) and three data sources including pregnant women (from France, Finland and Spain). The estimated lookback periods to identify 95% of MS cases ranged from 6 to 9 years. Prevalence calculation methods accounting for temporal variations returned lower prevalence estimates compared to method including all identified MS cases and study participants over the period. Careful consideration of lookback duration and data availability is essential for accurate prevalence estimation.</p>
<p>Marie Beslay, Anna-Belle Beau, Davide Messina, Justine Benevent, Elisa Ballardini, Laia Barrachina-Bonet, Clara Caverro-Carbonell, Alex Coldea, Laura García-Villodre, Anja Geldhof, Rosa Gini, Kerstin Hellwig, Sue Jordan, Maarit K Leinonen, Sandra Lopez-Leon, Marco Manfrini, Visa Martikainen, Vera R Mitter, Amanda J Neville, Hedvig Nordeng, Aurora Puccini, Sandra Vukusic, Christine Damase-Michel, Yvonne Geissbühler, Joan K Morris. Identifying multiple sclerosis in women of childbearing age in six European countries: A contribution from the ConcePTION project <i>Submitted to Eur. J Epidemiology</i></p>	<p>This study aimed to compare five algorithms to identify MS among women of childbearing age in six European healthcare data sources. The least restrictive algorithm (MS1), which required only one MS diagnosis or one dispensing for MS-specific DMT, provided prevalence estimates that most closely aligns with existing literature. This study demonstrates how different algorithms can be used to identify multiple sclerosis in women of childbearing age and pregnant women within healthcare data sources. It also provides new prevalence data for MS in European countries with good geographic spread. These insights could contribute to further research on MS medication use in women of childbearing age and pregnant women and on the safety of use of MS medication during pregnancy.</p>

DP4: Migraine: **Demonstrating solutions for studying intermittent medication exposures in diseases with episodic manifestations during pregnancy: application to medication for migraine in pregnancy**

Congress publications	Brief Summary of Findings
<p>Identification and characterization of migraine around pregnancy in population-based registries. Mitter VR, Lupattelli A, Bjørk MH, Nordeng HE. Poster presentation. ISPE Mid-Year Conference, April 24–25, 2023, Reykjavik, Iceland.</p>	<p>The prevalence of migraines identified was 2.9%–4.3% before, and 0.8%–1.5% during pregnancy, depending on algorithm used. Pregnant women with migraine were mostly managed in primary care.</p> <p>Primary care data in combination with drug dispensation records were instrumental for identification of migraine in electronic healthcare registries. Data from secondary care and drug dispensations allow better characterization of migraines. Jointly, these algorithms may contribute to improved perinatal pharmacoepidemiological studies in this population by addressing confounding by maternal migraine indication.</p>
<p>Algorithms to Identify Preeclampsia in European Healthcare Data Sources: A pilot study in Norway and Finland from the ConcePTION project. Mitter VR, Hoxhaj V, Mølgaard-Nielsen D, Navarro CA, Martikainen V, Lopez-Leon S, Leinonen MK, Nordeng HME: <i>Poster presentation. The 15th Annual NorPEN Meeting, November 22–24, 2023, Oslo, Norway.</i></p>	<p>The prevalence of preeclampsia ranged from 1.3% in Italy and Spain to 4.0% in Norway. The prevalence remained stable from 2009 to 2020. There was a slight variation between age groups.</p>
<p>Algorithms to Identify Gestational Diabetes in European Healthcare Data Sources: A pilot study in Norway and Finland from the ConcePTION project. Mølgaard-Nielsen D, Mitter VR, Hoxhaj V, Navarro CA, Martikainen V, Lopez-Leon S, Maarit K Leinonen, Nordeng HME: <i>Poster presentation. The 15th Annual NorPEN Meeting, November 22–24, 2023, Oslo, Norway.</i></p>	<p>In this multi-national study, GDM prevalence ranged from 1.3% to 15.8%, depending on the algorithm and data sources used. In the Nordic countries, the differences in GDM prevalence between the narrowest and broadest algorithms were relatively small, whereas in Southern Europe, these were significantly larger. These variations are likely due to differences in coding practices, healthcare systems, and database coverage. We recommend selecting algorithms based on the study's priorities—using narrow algorithms when high specificity is critical and broad algorithms when high sensitivity is more important.</p>
Publications	Brief Summary of Findings
<p>Sandra Lopez-Leon, Ditte Mølegaard-Nielsen, Vera R Mitter, Angela Lupattelli, Vjola Hoxhaj, Constanza Andaur Navarro, Saeed Hayati, Joan Morris, Maarit K Leinonen, Visa Martikainen,</p>	<p>The prevalence of preeclampsia ranged from 1.3% in Italy and Spain to 4.0% in Norway. The prevalence remained stable from 2009 to</p>

<p>Susan Jordan, Marco Manfrini, Laia Barrachina-Bonet, Clara Caverro-Carbonell, Anthony Caillet, Christine Damase-Michel, Marleen M.H.J. van Gelder, Hedvig Nordeng. Identifying Preeclampsia in European Electronic Healthcare Data: Insights from the ConcePTION Project <i>In preparation</i></p>	<p>2020. There was a slight variation between age groups.</p>
<p>Ditte Mølegaard-Nielsen, Vera R Mitter, Angela Lupattelli, Vjola Hoxaj, Constanza Andaur Navarro, Saeed Hayati, Sandra Lopez-Leon, Joan Morris, Susan Jordan, Maarit K Leinonen, Visa Martikainen, Marco Manfrini, Amanda Neville, Laia Barrachina-Bonet, Clara Caverro-Carbonell, Anthony Caillet, Christine Damase-Michel, Marleen M.H.J. van Gelder, Hedvig Nordeng. Identification of Gestational diabetes in European electronic healthcare data: Insights from the ConcePTION project <i>In preparation</i></p>	<p>In this multi-national study, GDM prevalence ranged from 1.3% to 15.8%, depending on the algorithm and data sources used. In the Nordic countries, the differences in GDM prevalence between the narrowest and broadest algorithms were relatively small, whereas in Southern Europe, these were significantly larger. These variations are likely due to differences in coding practices, healthcare systems, and database coverage. We recommend selecting algorithms based on the study's priorities—using narrow algorithms when high specificity is critical and broad algorithms when high sensitivity is more important.</p>

DP5: Incidence and survival of pregnancy associated breast cancer

<h3>Congress Publications</h3>	<h3>Brief Summary of Findings</h3>
<p>Krumme A, Mølgaard-Nielsen D, Martikainen V et al, Pregnancy and infant outcomes in gestationally-diagnosed breast cancer: A pilot study in Finland and Norway from the ConcePTION project. <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.</i> 2024;33 (S2): e5891. https://doi.org/10.1002/pds.5891</p>	<p>Women with gestational breast cancer delivered at earlier gestational age than women with non-gestational breast cancer but there was no evidence of intrauterine growth restriction.</p> <p>Pregnancies in women with gestationally-diagnosed breast cancer tended to be more often managed by Cesarean section. Limited breast cancer therapy options during pregnancy and concerns of disease progression may lead to earlier elective delivery. These findings contrast with treatment guidelines recommending carrying a pregnancy to full term as a management goal for breast cancer occurring in pregnancy.</p> <p>Results were based on the data from Finland and Norway.</p>

<p>Leinonen MK, Martikainen V, Campbell C et al, Incidence and survival of pregnancy associated breast cancer: A contribution from the ConcePTION project piloted in Finland and Norway, <i>Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf.</i> 2024;33 (S2): e5891. https://doi.org/10.1002/pds.5891</p>	<p>Patients with pregnancy associated breast cancer are at an increased risk of death which is driven by breast cancers arising in the postpartum period.</p> <p>Missing data reduces study power and may lead to survival estimates that are different from those that would have been obtained had no data been missing.</p> <p>Poorer prognosis of pregnancy associated breast cancer is largely, but not fully, explained by more adverse tumor characteristics.</p> <p>ISPE 2024 results were based on the data from Finland and Norway, NorPEN 2024 results included additional data from Spain, Valencia.</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Brief Summary of Findings</p>
<p>Krumme A, Mølgaard-Nielsen D, Martikainen V et al, Pregnancy and infant outcomes in gestationally-diagnosed breast cancer: A study from the IMI ConcePTION project. <i>In preparation.</i></p>	<p>Women with gestational breast cancer delivered at earlier gestational age than women with non-gestational breast cancer but there was no evidence of intrauterine growth restriction.</p> <p>Pregnancies in women with gestationally-diagnosed breast cancer tended to be more often managed by Cesarean section.</p> <p>Limited breast cancer therapy options during pregnancy and concerns of disease progression may lead to earlier elective delivery. These findings contrast with treatment guidelines recommending carrying a pregnancy to full term as a management goal for breast cancer occurring in pregnancy.</p>
<p>Leinonen MK, Martikainen V, Campbell C et al, Incidence and Survival of Pregnancy Associated Breast Cancer: a Contribution from the IMI ConcePTION Project. <i>In preparation.</i></p>	<p>Patients with pregnancy associated breast cancer are at an increased risk of death which is driven by breast cancers arising in the postpartum period.</p> <p>Missing data reduces study power and may lead to survival estimates that are different from those that would have been obtained had no data been missing.</p> <p>Poorer prognosis of pregnancy associated breast cancer is largely, but not fully, explained by more adverse tumor characteristics.</p>

Discussion

All demonstration projects in WP1 depended on the development of the ConcePTION pregnancy algorithm and data access providers' mapping of registry data onto the ConcePTION CDM. This was a major focus of work in WP1 and WP7 and required prioritizing the DPs' efforts to first complete the phenotype algorithms and then use the remaining time and resources for selected study objectives. This was done to ensure the overall scientific quality of the output of the work package.

In DP1, we developed algorithms to identify the maternal conditions related to gabapentinoid prescriptions in six European countries. We also explored the use of gabapentin and pregabalin during pregnancy. We then focused on assessing the teratogenicity of gabapentinoids using the EUROMediCAT database.

In DP2, we developed algorithms to identify maternal depression, ADHD, ASD, Intellectual Disability, in five electronic data sources; and Delayed Development and breast feeding in two data sources. We also assessed the teratogenicity of antidepressants using the EUROMediCAT database.

In DP3, we developed algorithms to identify MS among women of childbearing age and pregnant women, in six European countries. We also evaluated three distinct methods for calculating MS prevalence and assessed the impact of different lookback periods on prevalence estimates. Then, we explored the use of MS medications during pregnancy and investigated congenital anomalies linked to maternal MS and Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE), along with their associated treatments using the EUROMediCAT database.

In DP4, we focused on the maternal outcomes, preeclampsia and gestational diabetes as well as identification of migraine in electronic healthcare data sources.

In DP5, we focused on improving methods for inclusion of medicines administered at hospitals which are rarely available in European databases, specifically with respect to incidence and prevalence, disease management, safety of treatment, and survival of breast cancer in pregnancy.

Conclusion

Work Package 1 explored how to perform multinational studies on medications in pregnancy, in collaboration with European data access providers who had mapped their electronic health care registry data onto the ConcePTION CDM. Highly diverse European data sources and health care systems from Finland, France, Italy, Norway, Spain and Wales were included. Diseases like neuropathic pain, depression, migraine, MS, and pregnancy-associated breast cancers presenting different methodological challenges were addressed in the demonstration projects.